

EFFECT OF COMPETENCE IN MATHEMATICS ON NIGERIAN SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS' PERFORMANCE IN MOLE CONCEPT PROBLEMS IN CHEMISTRY

By

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Abstract

The study investigated the effect of Mathematical knowledge on of Nigerian Secondary School Students' performance in mole concept problems in Chemistry.

The sample comprised of Senior Secondary one Students, purposively selected from four secondary schools in Ilorin West and South Local Government Area of Kwara State. 120 students (60 males and 60 female were selected from two schools each serves as experimental and control groups respectively. The content scope of the study was restricted to mole concept of the Senior School Chemistry curriculum.

A quasi experimental, non-randomized, non-equivalent pretest post test control group was adopted for the study. The instruments used were a researchers developed Mathematics Competence Test (MCT) and a problem solving in mole concept Test (PSMCT). These Instruments were validated by three experts (three experienced Secondary School Chemistry Teachers who have been WAEC and NECO examiners) Two research questions were raised to guide the study. The data were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient Analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) and Duncan Multiple Range Test. The findings showed that there is a high significant relationship between students performance in mathematics and their performance in mole concept in chemistry, Students who scored very high in mathematics also scored very high in the mole concept in Chemistry.

Based on these findings it was recommended that teaching mole concept with mathematics emphasis can be used to enhance the performance of students in solving mole problems.

INTRODUCTION

Science, Technology and Mathematics play an important role in the development of any nation. Hence, more advancement in technology needs an increase in the science, technology and mathematics competence in day to day activities of all citizen (Jegade, 1983).

The inclusion of chemistry as a core subject in the sciences in the 6-3-3-4 educational system in Nigeria is justifiable considering its importance in other major disciplines or fields such as medicine, Pharmacy, Geology, Engineering, Agricultural Science and Science Education.

The study of the physical aspect of chemistry cannot be understood without a solid background in mathematics. This might have been the rationale for making mathematics compulsory and that no student can transit to the Senior Secondary School without passing it at the Junior School Certificate Examination (Ojerinde 1999). No nation can develop scientifically and yet neglect the mathematical component of the school curriculum. In fact, mathematics is the central intellectual discipline of all sciences and technological societies. Mathematics cannot be separated from the rest of the sciences and especially chemistry because without a credit in the two subjects, students cannot gain admission into courses such as Engineering, Computer Sciences and Medicine which require chemistry.

Unfortunately over the years the performance of students in the science subjects in the West African Senior School Certificate Examinations is not encouraging despite all the efforts of the Federal and State Government.

Literature Review

In chemistry, researchers like Adeyegbe 1993; Igwe, 1994; Olorundare, 2005; dossier, 1990, have identified poor performance of students in West African School Certificate Examination as due to the inability of students to understand some quantitative aspects of chemistry topics identified as difficult by Finley, Stewart and Yarnoch (1982). These include writing of chemical formulae, chemical equations,

mole concept, atomic structure, the arrangement of electrons in atoms and stoichiometry. Also Abdullahi and Aninyei (1983) observed that mole concept, electro chemistry, chemical equilibrium and solubility were difficult for students. Akinmade and Adisa (1984), Onwu and Ahiakwo (1986) reported that the mole and ions in solution were difficult for students to learn.

Furthermore, Friedel and Maloney (1992) showed that students had difficulties when working with chemical formulae and the mole concept. This shows that mole concept has been one of the difficult concept identified both within and outside Nigeria. Among the reasons given by students generally in Nigeria were poor background in mathematics, difficulty in recalling and representing or writing ionic equations, (Ahiakwo, 1984; Onwu&Moneme, 1986).

As a result of continuous poor performance in the sciences, the Nigerian Education Research and Development Council (NERDC) conducted a national workshop on difficult concepts in the sciences and Mathematics in Lagos in 1993. The first topic identified as difficult in chemistry by the members of the chemistry panel at the workshop was the mole concept (Ivowi, 1993). Among various reasons given for the difficulty were communication skills, students inability to read for understanding and to express themselves clearly, misconceptions of the mole by students because of their mathematical background, socio cultural values, abstract nature of the mole concept, technical language and terminologies and mathematical orientation of the mole concept and inadequate problem solving skills. Adeyegbe (2004) and Okebukola (2005) also identified mole concept as one of the topics that recent chemistry education graduates found difficult to teach.

The mole is a basic topic that requires students understanding of mathematics before problems can be solved in it. For instance, ratio, logarithms, fractions, substitution in formula equations, variations and percentages are some of the basic concepts in mathematics that students need to know very well before they can solve problems in mole concept. These topics are taught in the Junior Secondary School Mathematics for students to perform well in the sciences, especially chemistry at the

Senior Secondary Level. Out of these topics, logarithm, ratio and proportion had been identified as difficult topics by the mathematics panel at the workshop on difficult concepts in science and mathematics (Ivowi, 1993).

In addition, the mole concept is a foundation concept in chemistry that acts as a unity concept linking many aspects of the subject throughout the syllabus. For instance, other topics that the mole concept links to are chemical formulae, balancing of chemical equations, law of chemical combinations, reaction stoichiometry and quantitative aspects of electrolysis etc.

Considering the different topics, which the mole concept can help students to understand, it is proper to conclude that the concept of mole is a basic topic to successful learning of chemistry in the Senior School Chemistry curriculum. It involves solving of problems, students have to be competent in mathematics before they can perform very well in solving mole concept problems. Considering the importance of chemistry in all round development, there is need for fundamental topics like the mole concept to be properly understood and mathematical skill is necessary to make this understanding a reality.

The WAEC Chief Examiners reports (1996, 1997, 2002, 2003) observed that students have poor understanding of the mole concept, chemical arithmetic, inability to write the formula of atoms, molecules or ions as appropriate and balancing of equations correctly. They also show incompetence in handling numerical data and poor expression of chemical terms and calculations. Students tended to avoid questions on the mole concept and those who attempted them, usually performed poorly in them because of their abstractness and quantitative nature. Knowledge of mole concept helps to solve many problems. Kenni (2001) findings showed that there was a correlation between students' performance in mathematics and chemistry. However, the author failed to specify the nature of this correlation.

Etukudo and Nnaobi (2002) results showed that there was a positive correlation between the mathematics skill and learning of practical chemistry.

Furthermore, Ifamuyiwa (2004) findings showed that a significant correlation

existed between students performance in JSS mathematics and their performance in SS mathematics, further mathematics and physics respectively. Whether and how such a relationship manifests in learning difficult concepts in chemistry is yet to be determined.

The preceding discussions show that researchers have made several attempts at identifying difficult areas/topic in chemistry for students learning. Generally they have identified poor mathematical background, it was necessary, therefore to determine how enhanced mathematical background- would improve student's learning. It would be important to know if students performance in solving mole concept problems would improve if they are taught with mathematics emphasis as instructional strategy.

Research Questions.

1. What is the relationship between students' mathematical knowledge and their performance in the mole concept in chemistry?
2. What is the difference in the performance of chemistry students exposed to mole concept with mathematics emphasis and those exposed mole concept without mathematics emphasis?

Research hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between students' performance in mathematics and their performance in mole concept.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the - performance of chemistry students exposed to mole concept with mathematics emphasis and those exposed to mole concept without mathematics emphasis.

Methodology

The study employed a quasi-experimental, non-randomized, non-equivalent, pretest, posttest, control group. Two hundred and forty students (240) were selected

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SS I chemistry students from four secondary schools in Ilorin West and Ilorin East constituted the sample of the study. The sample had 120 students for the experimental and 120 students for the control group respectively.

The control groups were taught lessons on mole concept without mathematics emphasis while the experimental group was taught lessons on mole concept with mathematics emphasis. During this period the experimental group was taught mole concept in each of 40 minute lessons for four weeks using the lesson plan prepared by the researcher emphasizing on the mathematics skill. The control group teachers taught the control group separately using the guided lecture method or convectional method for the same number of periods and weeks.

Two instruments were used to collect relevant data for the study: A 40 item multiple choice questions in mathematics referred to as Mathematics Competence Test (MCT). These consist of questions related to solving mole concept problems and 40 items multiple choice questions in mole concept and 5 item theory question referred to as Problem Solving in Mole Concept Test (PSMCT). The PSMCT was drawn from past WAEC and NECO question papers and recommended chemistry textbooks.

The test items on chemistry were given to two science experts in the Science Education Department and one expert in Chemistry Department. Also three experienced Secondary School Chemistry teachers who are WAEC and NECO examiners. A pilot study was conducted using the two intact classes of a non participating school. The reliability of the research instruments were determined using Pearson product moment coefficient statistical method for the two test items. These were found to be 0.82 and 0.74 for the MCT and PSMCT respectively at 0.05 alpha levels. The data collected were analyzed using Pearson product moment correlation coefficient formula, t-test, analysis of covariance and mean gain scores.

Result

To answer research question one, the mean gain score is presented.

Table 1: the mean gain score of the students in mathematics and mole concept in chemistry.

Table 1: the mean gain score of the students in mathematics and mole concept in chemistry.

Variable	Number	mean of		
		Pre-test	Post Test	Gain score
Mathematics	240	47.813	53.142	5.329
Mole Concept in Chemistry	240	45.954	54.204	8.250

From table 1, it was observed that there was improvement in the performance of mathematics which also enhance improvement in the performance in chemistry. There is just a difference of 2.92 in. the mean gain score in the two subjects.

To answer the research question 2 the result of the Duncan Multiple Range Test was presented in table 2.

Table 2: Duncan Multiple Range Test showing the mean score of students in the experimented group and in the control group.

Group	Number	Mean score	Mean Difference
Mole concept without Mathematics emphasis	120	49.717	09.441
Mole concept with Mathematics emphasis	120	59.158	

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From table 2, it, was observed that the experimental group (mole concept with mathematics emphasis) performed better with mean score of (59.158) than the control group (mole concept without mathematics emphasis with mean score of (49.717). This showed that the treatment had a significant effect on the performance of the Chemistry students.

Hypothesis I was tested at 0.05 level of significance using Pearson product moment correlation coefficient and the results obtained is presented in table 3.

Table 3: Pearson Product Moment Correlation on Mathematics (MCT) and mole concept in chemistry (PSMCT) of students in the two groups.

Variable	Number of Cases	Mean	Standard Deviation	df	r value
Mathematics	240	100.9542	20.370	328	0.926
Mole conception	240	100.1583	18.378		

An r- value of 0.926 at alpha = 0.05 was obtained. Since this value is less than 1, the hypothesis 1 is rejected. This shows that there is high significant relationship between students' performance in mathematics and their performance in mole concept in chemistry. Students who scored very high in mathematics also scored very high in the mole concept in chemistry.

Hypothesis 2 was tested at 0.05 level of significance using Analysis of covariance in table 4.

Table 4: Results of Analysis of Covariance for Post Test scores of students in the experimental group and in the control group.

Source of variation	Sum of Square	df	Mean Square	F	Significance Level
Covariate Main effect	13446.29285	1	13446.2928	628.79	0.0001
Treatment	5348.70417	1	5348.70417	250.12	0.0001
Model	18794.997013	2	9397.498506	439.46	0.0001
Residual	5068.065487	237	21.1384243		
Total	23863.062500	239			

From table 4 $\alpha = 0.0001$. The value is less than 0.05

The null hypothesis is therefore rejected. This means that there is a significant difference in the performance of chemistry students exposed to mole concept with mathematics emphasis and those exposed to mole concept without mathematics emphasis. Students in the experimental group performed better than those in the control group. This means that teaching mole concept with mathematics as an instructional strategy was more effective in learning mole concept in chemistry than learning mole concept without mathematics emphasis.

Discussion and Recommendations

The main focus of this study was to examine the effect of mathematical knowledge on Nigerian Secondary School Students' performance in mole concept problems in chemistry. The findings of this study indicated a significant difference in the performance of students when taught with mathematically oriented teaching of

the mole concept. They performed better in the post test than their counterparts taught with conventional instructional strategy. This suggests that students' strong background in mathematics could actually help in their understanding of the mole concept in chemistry.

The result may not be surprising as Etukudo and Nnaobi (2002) had revealed a positive correlation between mathematics skill and learning of practical chemistry.

Also Badru (2004) examined student's performance in mathematics as correlates their performance in other basic science subjects. He found that the performance of students in the basic sciences influence their performance in mathematics, and that chemistry was the best subject to determine the performance in mathematics.

It is therefore a joint responsibility of both mathematics and science teachers to make sure that mathematics is not a barrier to students' understanding of science. With this, students would be able to recognize scientific problems and solve them with related mathematical background. The present study has affirmed that there is indeed a positive relationship between competence in mathematics and performance in chemistry and especially the mole concept.

This study was conducted so as to bring remedy to the problem of poor performance in chemistry and improvement in the understanding of mole concept as one of the identified difficult concept because of lack of competence in mathematics which is due to their poor background in mathematics. (Finley, Stewart and Yaroch, 1982).

The findings of this study have contributed to knowledge in the area of instructional strategies that promote problem solving in chemistry. The findings show that specific exposure of students to mathematics when teaching mole concept would enable them to solve mole concept problems step by step and this could improve the student's understanding of the topic and their performance in problem solving involving mole concept in chemistry.

Thus teachers would need to employ appropriate technique to solve mole

concept problems in a step by step manner that would make it easier for the students to solve other problems related to it independently. So that the chemistry teachers should expose students to mathematically oriented teaching of mole concept. This would improve their background, knowledge and ability to perform better in solving mole concept problems.

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